

Fermat's Last Theorem:

$$(X, Y, Z) = (Z - R^n, RA, Z)$$

additional proof(v3)

Therefore $(Z - X)$ must be n -th power.

$$Z - X = R^n$$

It means that

$$Z \equiv X \pmod{R^n}$$

And let $R = p_1 \times p_2 \times \cdots \times p_k$

Since $(Z - X)$ is a multiple of R^n ,

$(Z - X)$ is also a multiple of p_i .

$$X^n + R^n A^n = Z^n$$

$$X^n \equiv Z^n \pmod{R^n}$$

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It means

$$X^n \equiv Z^n \pmod{p_i}$$

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Therefore the period of X, Z is p_i .

But by Fermat's little theorem,

$$X^n \equiv X \pmod{n}$$

Therefore the period of X is n .

It is contradiction because R, n are coprime each other,
so the period of X, Z cannot be n or p_i at the same time.

One of them is impossible.

Add)

Since X must be satisfy $X = Z - R^n$,

Y also have to satisfy $Y = Z - L^n$. L is coprime to R .

And R and L cannot be 1 at the same time.

Because

$$(Z - 1)^n + (Z - 1)^n = Z^n$$

$$2(Z - 1)^n = Z^n$$

2 is not a n -th power, so it is contradiction.

Therefore at least one of R, L is bigger than 1.

$$R \geq 2 \text{ or } L \geq 2$$

Therefore one of R, L has a prime number $p \geq 2$
as a prime factor.

So it is impossible.

Thank you for reading.